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Sustainability Reporting And Market Capitalization: Implications For Listed Industrial Goods Companies In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

It is quite worrisome that most companies particularly in Nigeria are not fully committed to the environment and society where they derive resources for their economic activities and they do not also have the desire to empower and promote corporate responsiveness to other stakeholders. The main objective of this study was to examine the effect of sustainability disclosures on market capitalization of listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria from 2014 to 2023. The research design adopted for the study was ex post facto, secondary data were employed and purposive sampling technique was adopted to select 11 out of 13 listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. The ordinary least square regression analysis was used in analysing the data and the statistical package employed was STATA 14.2. The findings of the study revealed that economic sustainability disclosures have significant positive effect on market capitalization of listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria and governance sustainability disclosures have significant positive effect on market capitalization of listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria. Thus, it was concluded that sustainability disclosures have significant effect on market capitalization of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. Based on these findings, it was recommended that the management of industrial goods companies should continuously disclose their economic and governance strides as these disclosure practices attract investors and improve their market capitalization.

Keywords: Sustainability reporting, market capitalization, economic disclosures, geographical disclosures

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Sustainability reporting has emerged as a significant area of interest for businesses, investors and stakeholders globally and companies are now increasing aware that sustainability practices drive long term value creation and foster sustainable growth. Adapting organizations (especially firms) to their environments signifies a reciprocal or symbiotic relationship between the “duos” as typified by systems

model of viewing business. Considering the current environmental crisis, businesses must give more to their environments (Yondrichs et al., 2021). There are continuing concerns about nature's fragmentation and loss of biodiversity, shortages in freshwater availability, over-fishing of the seas, global warming, extreme weather conditions, air pollution, water pollution, environmental noise and utter neglect and disregard for the protection of the immediate environment, much more the future of environment. These types of environmental unsustainability associated with continuously rising demand and a shrinking resource base now spills over into social and economic instability (Lee et al., 2022). Therefore, many stakeholders are looking at business to be part of the solutions. For instance, Onyegbula (2021) maintained that business seems content to see the natural system on the planet disintegrating, people starving and social structures falling apart. Business was central to the problem and must be central to the solution. Indeed, the expectations of corporate sustainability responsibility in areas such as environmental protection, human rights, human capital development, and product safety are rising rapidly. Key stakeholders such as shareholders, employees, and financial institutions want businesses to be responsible, accountable, and transparent. Shaban and Barakat (2023). on the other hand, stated that human activities taking place today are regarded by some people as having a detrimental impact on the society, ecology, and economy which future generations would experience.

Economic sustainability disclosure is a set of practices and strategies that aim to create long term economic growth and development while also considering the social, and cultural aspects of a community (Akpan & Simeon, 2021; Shaban & Barakat, 2023). It is a key component of the international sustainable goals (SDGs). Economic sustainability strategies can improve financial performance by boosting innovation, operational efficiency, sales and marketing, customer loyalty, risk management, employee relations, media coverage and stakeholder engagement. Economic sustainability disclosure can also affect performance through cost and savings optimization, decision-making facilitation and improved corporate confidence and reputation. Governance sustainability disclosure refers to the communication of all relevant information about the functions of the company and its leadership to the stakeholders through annual reports and other documentaries (Shaban & Barakat, 2023). The impact of corporate governance disclosure on share price can be significant, as it influences investors' confidence, risk perception, and long-term value creation. According to Cheng et al. (2024) corporate governance disclosure promotes transparency by providing shareholders with insight into how the company is managed and controlled. This transparency can help build trust among investors, reduce information asymmetry, and increase confidence in the company's management practices, potentially leading to higher stock prices and increased shareholder wealth.

Market capitalization is a critical performance indicator for companies in the manufacturing sector, and it is influenced by various factors such as sustainability disclosure practices, financial performance, growth prospects, and market positions (Ubokudom et al., 2024). Companies that provide transparent and reliable sustainability reports attract socially responsible investors; and institutional investors seeking to align their portfolio with sustainability goals. This access to capital and increase demand for shares can lead to higher valuation and increase in market capitalization. In the view of Mutalib et al (2020), firm's market value is influenced by investors' perceptions of its managers' ability to anticipate and respond to future changes in the firm's economic environment.

Corporate disclosures have been an essential tool for communication between the company and stakeholders. However, rapid social and economic changes led to variations in the expectations of stakeholders. Companies in the world are putting up efforts to add values to their companies' bottom lines by engaging in sustainable business practices. However, it is quite worrisome that most companies particularly in Nigeria are not fully committed to the environment and society where they derive resources for their economic activities and they do not also have the desire to empower and promote corporate responsiveness to other stakeholders. A firm's perceived negligence or irresponsible environmental behavior can lead to regulatory sanctions, hostility from host community, long-term negative reputation in the eyes of the investors, customers and the suppliers; and could ultimately result in the firm being less attractive in the market thus making investors to lose confidence in such firms. From

the review of empirical studies, it was found out that the previous studies used other performance measures like EPS, ROA, ROE, Tobins Q, market capitalization and so on (Etim & Akpan, 2023; Dincer et al., 2024; Agarwal et al., 2023., Iliemena et al., 2023; Friske et al., 2022). Thus, it was against the above identified gaps that this study was undertaken to ascertain the effect of corporate sustainability disclosures on market value of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

Sustainability reporting

Dow Jones sustainability index in KPMG (2020) looked at sustainability reporting as a business approach that created long term shareholder value by embracing opportunities and managing risks deriving from economic, environmental, and social developments. It can be synonymous with triple bottom line reporting, corporate responsibility reporting and sustainable development reporting, but increasingly, these terms have become more specific in meaning and therefore, subsets of sustainability reporting (Etim et al., 2023). Sedeaz (2024) defined corporate sustainability disclosure as a subset of accounting and reporting that deals with activities, methods, and systems to record, analyses and report, firstly, environmentally, and socially induced financial impacts and secondly, ecological, and social impacts of a defined economic system (example, a company, production site, and nation). Thirdly, Sustainability Reporting dealt with the measurement, analysis and communication of interactions and links between social, environmental, and economic issues constituting the three dimensions of sustainability. Sustainability was first coined as “Sustain-Ability” by John Elkington, the founder of a British Consultancy in 1994 (Effiong et al., (2019). His argument was that companies should be responsible for preparing three different (and quite separate) bottom lines.

Market capitalization

Market capitalization refers to the total value of all a company's shares of stock. It is defined as a company's stock value multiplied by its total number of shares outstanding (Hart, 2019). Market capitalization allows investors to evaluate a company based on how valuable the public perceives it to be. The increase or decrease in market capitalization depends on the movement of investors' confidence and perception. The movement of investors' confidence toward a particular company depends on the positive information of that company. Market capitalization represents the total value of a company's outstanding shares of stock and is calculated by multiplying the current market price per share by the total number of shares outstanding. Investors who value sustainable and socially responsible practices may be more inclined to invest in firms that demonstrate a commitment to sustainability practices (Onyegbula, 2021). This increased investor demand can potentially drive up the stock price and subsequently increase the market capitalization of the firm. Firms that provide comprehensive and transparent information, follow recognized reporting frameworks such as the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI), or obtain third-party certifications may experience a stronger positive impact on market capitalization (Osuagwu & Okoyeuzu, 2020). In addition, the extent of influence environment voluntary disclosure has on market capitalization depends on various factors, including the quality and credibility of disclosure, industry competitiveness, and investor expectations as suggested by Adenugba et al., (2018). A share, as a stock exchange security, acts as proof of ownership. Investors were willing to pay a specified price for a stock in exchange for more earnings than they earned from previous capital stock purchases (Abdullah & Suryanto, 2023).

Economic sustainability disclosure and market capitalization

Economic sustainability disclosure is a set of practices and strategies that aim to create long term economic growth and development while also considering the social, and cultural aspects of a community (Shaban & Barakat, 2023). It is a key component of the international sustainable goals (SDGs). Economic sustainability is when an activity, financial or not, helps to support long-term financial growth without negatively impacting social, environment al and cultural aspect of the community (Iliemena et al., 2023). Umeanozie and Ofoegbu, (2022) who investigated corporate sustainability practices and corporate market capitalization found that economic performance insignificant effect on market capitalization. The study of

Friske et al. (2021) also found an existing relationship between economic sustainability and financial performance. Similarly, Hussain (2022) and Etim and Akpan (2023) found a positive effect of economic disclosures on market value when measured using Tobins q

Governance sustainability disclosures and market capitalization

Governance sustainability disclosure refers to the communication of all relevant information about the functions of the company and its leadership to the stakeholders through annual reports and other documentaries (Shaban & Barakat, 2023). Corporate governance disclosure (CGD) refers to the extent to which an organization transparently and truthfully communicates its governance policies and strategies to stakeholders (UNCTAD, 2011). Akpan and Simeon (2021) examined the effect of sustainability disclosures on cash flow return on investment of shareholders of oil and gas companies in Nigeria. Employing cross sectional analysis, they found that economic disclosures have significant effect on cash flow return on investment of oil and gas companies in Nigeria. **Friske et al.** (2021) on the other hand, studied to determine the effect of sustainability reporting on market value of quoted oil and gas firms in Nigeria and found that sustainability reporting has a significant positive effect on return on equity, net profit margin and earnings per share. In the same vein, Effiong et al. (2019) while studying the effect of triple bottom line disclosures on economic value added, market value added and cash flow return on investment of oil and gas companies in Nigeria found a positive effect among these variables. From review of related literature, Ogochukwu and Grace (2022) found a positive significant relationship between governance disclosures and EVA. Iliemena et al. (2023) discovered a significant positive relationship between corporate governance disclosure and average market price per share; Also, Xie et al. (2019), Gompers et al. (2023) found positive relationship between governance disclosure and financial performance. Contrary findings exist in Rouf (2022) who found negative relationship between governance disclosure and financial performance; Warren and Thomsen (2022) found a negative relationship between governance disclosures and firm value. Based on this evidence, this study hypothesized that;

3.0 METHODOLOGY

This research adopted ex post facto research design because the data used were obtained from the annual reports of the studied companies. The population of the study was 13 while purposive sampling technique was used to select 11 industrial goods companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group. The secondary data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics, correlation and regression analysis. The companies’ market value was measured as the product of year end market price per share and year end outstanding shares, while sustainability reporting was measured using content analysis where ‘1’ was given where the sustainability item was disclosed and ‘0’ where there was no disclosure. The model for this study is adopted from the studies of Akpan and Simeon (2021) but modified to suit the hypotheses of this study. As stated below;

$$\text{Market capitalization} = f(\text{economic disclosures and governance disclosures}) \quad (2)$$

$$MCAP_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ECNDI_{it} + \beta_2 GODI_{it} + \beta_5 FIMZ_{it} + \mu_{it}$$

Where:

- MCAP = Market capitalization
- ECNDI = Economic sustainability disclosure
- GODI = Governance sustainability disclosure
- FSIZ = Firm size (control variable)
- “{i}” = Cross section (Sample companies)
- “t” = Time frame (2014-2023)
- u = Stochastic error Term

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Table 4.1 Descriptive statistics of sustainability disclosures and market capitalization of industrial goods companies listed in Nigeria

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Mcap (N'000)	110	3.713e+08	1.098e+09	134085.4	5.380e+09
Ecndi	110	.541	.191	.125	1
Godi	110	.512	.174	.125	.875
Totalassets (N'000)	110	3030024.6	5603919.3	42640	17040507

Source: Stata 14 output (2025)

Table 4.1 above shows the descriptive statistics of all the variables utilized in this study. From the top we have market capitalization (MCAP) which showed an average of N371,300,000 and a standard deviation of N1,098,000,000. This means the data points are not clustered if plotted on a scatter graph as the standard deviation was relatively large and far from the mean. Also, firms in the industrial goods sector have at least N134,085.40 and at most N5,380,000,000 as their market capitalization. Table 4.1 also revealed that economic sustainability disclosure (ECNDI) had an average of 0.541 which is about 4 out of 8 items on the index. This indicates an average or medium level of concern or concentration given to economic sustainability issues in the industrial goods industry. The lowest index score ever recorded in the aspect of economic sustainability disclosure (ECNDI) was 0.125; indicating that at some year, some company did not really take economic sustainability as a serious issue as this was only 1 item out of 8. The highest ever recorded between 2014 and 2023 was 1; meaning 8 out of 8 items. Also, governance sustainability disclosure (GODI) presented 0.512 as mean index score; implying 4 out of 8 items still, as in those of environmental, social and economic. This came with a standard deviation of 0.174 which still showed low degree of variability in the scores of each firm. This means the score for each firm clustered around and not far from the mean and that similar practice exist in each sampled firm. Highest and lowest scores for the index at the time were 0.875 (7) and 0.125 (1) respectively. However, this particular indicator did not have a maximum score of 1 like the other indicators, however, 0.875 is not a bad high score at all, just one thing missed.

Table 4.2 Spearman's rank correlation coefficients

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
(1)	1.000			
mcaplog				
(2) ecndi	0.138	1.000		
(3) godi	0.179	0.213	1.000	
(4) fsiz	0.789	0.214	0.229	1.000

Source: Stata 14 output (2024)

Table 4.4 shows coefficients for the spearman correlation and it was observed that each of the variables had perfect correlation with themselves with 1.000 as correlation coefficient. Economic sustainability disclosure (ECNDI) exhibited weak positive association (0.138) with market capitalization of listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria, implying that increased economic sustainability disclosures usually comes with increased market capitalization in the sampled firms, and at the same time, this increase in market capitalization is not caused by the increase in economic sustainability disclosures. For governance sustainability disclosure (GODI), 0.179 was the case, indicating a weak positive correlation with market capitalization of listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria. This implies that when governance sustainability disclosures increase, market capitalization also happens to increase to a low extent. In summary, these results indicate the absence of multicollinearity since all the associations are seen to be weak apart from that of firm size. Now, this is normal and was expected because it's actually true in logical sense.

Regression analysis

Table 4.3 Regression analysis for the effect of sustainability disclosures on market capitalization of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria.

Variables	Coefficients	P> z/t	Lagrange	Hausman	Hetest	VIFs	R ²
Pooled OLS							
ecndi	0.017	0.398			11.21(0.001)	1.080	0.551
godi	0.128	0.010			10.41(0.001)	1.080	0.757
Random Effects GLS							
ecndi	0.119	0.024	6.09(0.000)	0.05(0.975)			0.655
godi	0.128	0.071	5.39(0.001)	0.06(0.9684)			0.697
Fixed Effects GLS							
ecndi	0.018	0.389					0.455
godi	0.029	0.207					0.697
Random Effects (with robust standard errors)							
ecndi	0.170	0.003					0.683
godi	0.128	0.032					0.657

Source: Author’s compilation of Stata output (2025)

Results from the robust random effects GLS in table 4.3 presented the following results: economic sustainability disclosure (ecndi) model presented an R squared of 0.683, entailing that 68.3% of the variations in market capitalization could be explained by economic sustainability disclosure and firm size. The remaining 31.7% was also attributed to the error term. Lastly, governance sustainability disclosure (godi), alongside firm size (fsiz) accounted for 65.7% of changes in market capitalization (mcap). The remaining part is captured in the error term (34.3%).

The study tested for heteroscedasticity, variance inflation factor (multicollinearity), as well as the Lagrange multiplier test. The one with robust standard errors was later used to account for heteroscedasticity for ecndi model. Heteroscedasticity was present (11.21[0.001]), no multicollinearity (1.08), random effect was suitable due to the Lagrange test (6.09[0.000]). Lastly, for godi model, there was no homoscedasticity (10.41[0.001]).

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

4.4.3 Economic sustainability disclosure and market capitalization

The results obtained from the ECNDI’s robust random effects regression model revealed that economic sustainability disclosure (ECNDI) has a coefficient of 0.170 with a p-value of 0.003, indicating a statistically significant positive effect on the market capitalization of listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria. This finding suggests that firms which prioritize and transparently report on economic sustainability initiatives tend to experience higher market valuations. In other words, an increase in the economic sustainability disclosure index scores of these firms is associated with a corresponding increase in their market capitalization. The positive and statistically significant coefficient not only underscores the relevance of economic sustainability disclosures but also aligns with the apriori expectation that firms with better economic performance and transparency are rewarded by the market. Another reason for the positive effect of economic sustainability disclosure on market capitalization could be the growing emphasis on sustainable investment strategies among institutional investors. As global financial markets shift towards incorporating environmental, social, and governance (ESG) criteria into their investment decisions, firms that excel in economic sustainability are likely to attract more capital.

From the literature, Nkanga et al. (2023) and Dobers (2021) highlighted that sustainability disclosures, including economic performance metrics, have become crucial in assessing a company’s long-term value creation.

4.4.4 Governance sustainability disclosure and market capitalization

The results from the GODI's robust random effects regression model revealed that governance sustainability disclosure (GODI) has a coefficient of 0.128 with a p-value of 0.032, indicating a statistically significant positive effect on the market capitalization of listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria. The positive coefficient suggests that as companies increase their governance sustainability disclosure scores, there is a corresponding increase in their market capitalization. In simpler terms, firms that are more transparent and proactive in their governance-related disclosures tend to enjoy higher market valuations, reflecting investor confidence in the management and oversight mechanisms of these firms. The significant positive relationship between governance sustainability disclosure and market capitalization can be attributed to several factors. Firstly, effective governance practices are linked to reduced agency problems, where management acts in the best interests of shareholders rather than pursuing personal gains. By disclosing information on governance structures and practices, firms signal their commitment to transparency, accountability, and ethical conduct, thereby reducing information asymmetry between management and investors. This increased transparency can boost investor trust, leading to greater investment inflows and higher market valuations. This study which revealed a significant positive effect of governance sustainability disclosure on market capitalization, is consistent with several prior studies in the literature. For instance, Etim and Akpan (2023) and Cheng et al. (2024) highlighted that comprehensive corporate governance disclosures enhance transparency, build investor trust, and reduce information asymmetry, ultimately leading to increased shareholder confidence and higher stock prices. This aligns with the current study's observation that higher levels of governance disclosure positively influence the market valuation of listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria. Similarly, Nkanga et al (2023) and Gompers et al. (2023) noted that firms with strong governance practices are better at managing risks, thereby attracting institutional investors who prioritize transparency and accountability. This influx of institutional ownership can enhance share liquidity and stability, which supports a positive market response to robust governance disclosures.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Sustainability reporting is a very important aspect of firms' valuation as investors react positively to companies that disclose their sustainability strides indicating corporate responsiveness towards the environment and community where they operate. The analysis demonstrated that governance and economic sustainability disclosures has significant positive effects on the market capitalization of the sampled firms, suggesting that companies that prioritize and transparently report on these areas are rewarded with higher valuations. Firms that provide detailed governance disclosures, showcasing their commitment to transparency and accountability are perceived favourably in the market. The positive impact of economic sustainability disclosures further highlights the importance of demonstrating financial resilience and contributions to the local economy. Thus, this study concluded that sustainability disclosures can significantly influence investors' perception and thus the market value of industrial goods firms in Nigeria. Based on these findings, it was recommended that the management of industrial goods companies should continuously disclose their economic and governance strides as these disclosure practices attract investors and improve market valuation.

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